

Appendix A. Legal Sources and Comparative Regulatory Framework on Cyberbullying

Country	Regulation	Article	Contents of the article	Source
Indonesia	Law Number 1 of 2024 concerning Electronic Information and Transactions and the Criminal Code	Article 27A	What is meant by 'attacking the honor or name of a bailiff' is an act that degrades or damages the reputation or self-esteem of another person, thereby causing harm to that person, including insulting and/or slandering.	https://peraturan.bpk.go.id/details/274494/uu-no-1-tahun-2024
		Article 27B paragraph (1)	What is meant by 'threat of violence' is Electronic Information and/or Electronic Documents containing content intended to cause fear, anxiety, or concern about the occurrence of violence.	
		Article 27B paragraph (2)	What is meant by 'threat of defamation' is a threat to attack the honor or reputation of another person by accusing something with the intention that it becomes publicly known.	
		Article 29	What is meant by 'victim' is a person who experiences physical, mental, and/or economic suffering caused by a criminal act. Included in the acts referred to in this provision is harassment in digital spaces (cyberbullying).	
South Korea	Act on promotion of information and communications network utilization and information protection	Article 44 paragraph (1): 1-3	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. No user may circulate any information violative of other person's rights, including invasion of privacy and defamation, through an information and communications network. 2. Every provider of information and communications services shall make efforts to prevent any information under paragraph (1) from being circulated through the information and communications network operated and managed by it. 3. The Korea Communications Commission may prepare a policy on technological development, education, public relations activities, and other activities to prevent violation of other persons' rights by information circulated through information and communications networks, including invasion of privacy and defamation, and may recommend 	https://elaw.klri.re.kr/eng_service/lawView.do?lang=ENG&hseq=7288

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		Article 44 paragraph (2): 1-4	<p>providers of information and communications services to adopt the policy.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> <li data-bbox="989 300 1664 619">1. Where information provided through an information and communications network purposely to be made public intrudes on other persons' privacy, defames other persons, or violates other persons' right otherwise, the victim of such violation may request the provider of information and communications services who managed the information to delete the information or publish a rebuttable statement (hereinafter referred to as "deletion or rebuttal"), presenting explanatory materials supporting the alleged violation. <li data-bbox="989 624 1664 943">2. A provider of information and communications services shall, upon receiving a request for deletion or rebuttal of the information under paragraph (1), delete the information, take a temporary measure, or any other necessary measure, and shall notify the applicant and the publisher of the information immediately. In such cases, the provider of information and communications services shall make it known to users that he/she has taken necessary measures by posting a public notification on the relevant message board or in any other way. <li data-bbox="989 948 1664 1362">3. provider of information and communications services shall, if there is any unwholesome medium for juvenile published in violation of the labeling method under Article 42 in the information and communications network operated and managed by him/her or if a content advertising any unwholesome medium for juvenile is displayed in such network without any measures to restrict access by juvenile under Article 42-2, delete such content without delay. (4) A provider of information and communications services may, if it is difficult to judge whether information violates any right or it is anticipated that there will probably be a dispute between interested parties, take a measure to block access to the information 	

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			temporarily (hereinafter referred to as "temporary measures"), irrespective of a request for deletion of the information under paragraph (1). In such cases, the period of time for the temporary measure shall not exceed 30 days.	
		Article 44 paragraph (3)	A provider of information and communications services may, if it finds that information circulated through the information and communications network operated and managed by him/her intrudes on someone's privacy, defames someone, or violates someone's rights, take temporary measures at its discretion	
		Article 44 paragraph (6)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A person who alleges that information published or circulated by a specific user has intruded on his/her privacy, defamed him/her, or violated his/her rights may file a claim with the defamation dispute conciliation division under Article 44-10 to demand the relevant provider of information and communications services to furnish the information he/she possesses about the alleged offender (referring to the minimum information specified by Presidential Decree, including the name and address, necessary for filing a civil or criminal complaint), along with materials supporting his/her allegation of the violation, in order to file a civil or criminal complaint against the alleged offender. 2. The defamation dispute conciliation division shall, upon receiving a claim under paragraph (1), make a decision on whether to furnish information, hearing the opinion of the relevant user, unless it is impossible to contact the relevant user or there is any particular reason otherwise. 3. A person who receives information about the relevant user under paragraph (1) may not use the information for any purpose other than the purpose of filing a civil or criminal complaint. 	

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			<p>4. Other matters necessary for the contents of a claim to furnish information of a user and the procedure therefor shall be prescribed by Presidential Decree.</p>	
		Article 44 paragraph (7): 1-9	<p>No one may circulate information falling under any of the following subparagraphs through an information and communications network:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Information with an obscene content distributed, sold, rented, or displayed openly in the form of code, words, sound, image, or motion picture; 2. Information with a content that defames other persons by divulging a fact, false fact, openly and purposely to disparage the person's reputation; 3. Information with a content that arouses fear or apprehension by reaching other persons repeatedly in the form of code, words, sound, image, or motion picture; 4. Information with a content that mutilates, destroys, alters, or forges an information and communications system, data, a program, or similar or that interferes with the operation of such system, data, program, or similar without a justifiable ground; 5. Information with a content that falls within an unwholesome medium for juvenile under the Juvenile Protection Act and that is provided for profit without fulfilling the duties and obligations under relevant statutes, including the duty to verify the opposite party's age and the duty of labeling; 6. Information with a content that falls within speculative activities prohibited by statutes; 6-2. Information regarding content of transactions of personal information in violation of this Act or other statutes concerning the protection of personal information; 7. Information with a content that divulges a secret classified by statutes or any other State secret; 8. Information with a content that commits an activity prohibited by the National Security Act; 	

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			9. Other information with a content that attempts, aids, or abets to commit a crime	
		Article 70 paragraph (1-3)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> <li data-bbox="989 304 1664 491">1. A person who commits defamation of another person by disclosing a fact to the public through an information and communications network purposely to disparage his/her reputation shall be punished by imprisonment with labor for up to three years, or by fine not exceeding 30 million won. <li data-bbox="989 496 1664 715">2. A person who commits defamation of another person by disclosing a false fact to the public through an information and communications network purposely to disparage his/her reputation shall be punished by imprisonment with labor for up to seven years, by suspension of qualification for up to ten years, or by fine not exceeding 50 million won. <li data-bbox="989 719 1664 815">3. The public prosecution may not prosecute a person who committed a crime under paragraph (1) or (2) against the victim's will explicitly manifested. 	
		Article 70-2	A person who conveys or spread a malicious program in violation of Article 48 (2) shall be punished by imprisonment with labor of up to seven years or by fine not exceeding 70 million won.	
		Article 71 paragraph (11)	A person who mutilates another person's information or who infringes, misappropriates, or divulges another person's secret in violation of Article 49.	
		Article 72 paragraph (1):2	A person falling under any of the following subparagraphs shall be punished by imprisonment with labor for up to three years or by a fine not exceeding 30 million won	
		Article 73 paragraph (7)	A person who entices another person to furnish him/her with personal information in violation of Article 49-2 (1)	
		Article 74 paragraph (1):2-3	Any of the following persons shall be punished by imprisonment with labor for up to one year or by a fine not exceeding 10 million won	

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			<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. A person who distributes, sells, lends, or openly displays any obscene codes, letters, sound, images, or motion pictures in violation of Article 44-7 (1) 1; 3. A person who makes any codes, letters, sound, images, or motion pictures arousing fear or apprehension reach another person repeatedly in violation of Article 44-7 (1) 3; 	
	Act on prevention of and countermeasures against violence in schools	Article 2 (1):3	The term “cyber-bullying” means any form of constant or repeated actions whereby students inflict emotional harm on other students by using the Internet, cell phones or other information and communications devices to reveal personal information about a specific student or to spread lies or rumors about a specific student, and then inflict pain thereon;	https://media.unesco.org/sites/default/files/webform/r2e002/9856d00def025aeb4a59ecae0b8f8661874c0910.pdf
Article 17		<p>the administrative sanctions for perpetrators of cyberbullying crimes in the form of:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Order to provide a written apology to the victim student; 2. Prohibition on contacting, threatening, or retaliating against student victims and students who have reported, or informed on, violence at school; 3. Services to schools; 4. Service to the community; 5. Completing special education courses or receiving psychological treatment from internal or external experts; 6. Suspension of attendance; 7. Class changes; 8. Move to another school; 		

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			9. Expulsion from school.	
Japan	Penal Code of Japan or Japanese Criminal Code (刑法 keihō) Law No. 45 of 1907	Article 310	cyberbullying is a complaint offense, namely, the victim of cyberbullying must file a complaint/report of the bullying experienced for it to be processed legally as a complaint-based offense	https://www.cas.go.jp/jp/seisaku/hourei/data/PC.pdf
		Article 39	of the Keihō, encourages medical and normative assessments of perpetrators and mental disorders (shinsin sōshitsu), with the option of rehabilitation as an alternative to criminal punishment	
		Article 222	maximum penalty of two years' imprisonment or a fine of up to 500,000 yen. Article 230 addresses defamation, with penalties of up to 3 years' imprisonment or a fine of up to 500,000 yen, and Article 231 addresses insult, with fines of up to 10,000 yen or detention for up to 30 days.	

Source: Researcher's Process (2025)